

The AMPERE project: development of innovative European heterojunction bifacial cell and module technology in an industrial automated manufacturing plant.

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Abstract — Aim of AMPERE is the setting-up of an European sustainable manufacturing full-scale automated industrial pilot line, to produce bifacial heterojunction technology (HJT) silicon solar cells and modules. In this work we illustrate the state of art of AMPERE project, started in May 2017, focusing on its technical results, industrial and economic sustainability and perspectives on LCOE in the frame of vertical integration along with EGP as its natural end-user. These expected outcomes will be assessed and evaluated as a solid backbone to pave the way to the GW factory scaling up. The decision to accelerate in the project timeframe, within 2019, the installation and start-up of a manufacturing line, leading to a nominal capacity of EGP Catania 3SUN site to 200 MWp, will support the demonstration of the viability of HJT solar module massive production in Europe.

I. INTRODUCTION

2018-December: European solar industry trade body SolarPower Europe has said it has started a major campaign to bring back at least 5GW of large-scale PV manufacturing in the region, including the complete supply chain required to support the scheme. The European association estimates the demand for solar is set to rise soon to around 15GW a year in Europe. It is the time to see a concerted effort to sustain the development of every segment of the industrial European value chain, from wafer manufacturing to cells and modules production, in the coming years [1].

Today, facing the strong international competition leading to continuous price reductions, EU must seize the opportunities for the development of a novel PV industrial activity focusing in further technological innovation and optimization of entire supply chain, changing the key metric in PV through the shift of the focus from cost per watt to Levelised Cost of Electricity (LCOE).

In this framework, AMPERE project, started in 2017, aims to develop a fully automated manufacturing of latest-generation bifacial heterojunction photovoltaic cells and

modules, supporting the Enel Green Power project to transform its PV production technology, originally based on multi-junction thin-film silicon [2]. The expected impact is to regain the competitiveness in the entire EU PV value chain thanks to a unique consortium, with worldwide experience in the field of coatings, HJT cells and modules processing, which capitalize on one decade of advanced industrialization and development in the PV sector [3].

II. AMPERE OBJECTIVES AND PROJECT DESCRIPTION

The final goal of the AMPERE project is the setting-up of an innovative full-scale automated 200MWp/y production line of HJT bifacial cells and modules at the Enel Green Power 3SUN fab in Catania (Italy) and at the same time deliver the route to the GW fab scaling-up. The technologies developed in the project represent an innovation with respect to the market situation and with respect to the current practice in Industry: HJT is a very attractive candidate to compete against Asian mainstream technologies, in terms of both performances and module reliability. HJT solar cells are intrinsically bifacial cells with high ratio between back side and front side efficiency (> 92 % to 100 %). The reduced losses, due to low temperature coefficient, and cell bifaciality enable to achieve key performance gain in the field, with higher energy yield than mainstream technologies [4].

The project will respond to the EU requirements to support a sustainable growth addressing all the pillars of the sustainability concept: People (social sector), Planet (environmental sector), and Profit (economic sector). As these pillars are often interconnected, the actions adopted in one sector could contribute to maximize the effect of the expected impact in a different sector.

Fig. 1. AMPERE's consortium roles & organization (bottom) and business plan model (up).

The project operates (Fig.1) with the support of the technological platforms for solar cells at CEA-INES and the platform for advanced module technologies at Meyer Burger, along with the support of high level research institutes (CSEM, EPFL, Fraunhofer-ISE, ENEA, CNR, ERM), as well as key EU companies covering the whole PV value chain, namely Norsun for wafer preparation, Jonas & Redman for automation systems, Semilab for metrology on the front end side and Enel Green Power for the PV fields installation on the end-user energy operators' side.

In order to achieve its objectives AMPERE project is developed in 8 Work Packages (WP) over a timeframe of 36 months. WP1 holds the management and coordination actions that will support all the activities of the project in a coherent and smooth manner. The whole project and after-project success is guided by WP2 with a study of the economic aspect and the associated business models. The economical WP2 assess the sustainability of technical WPs. Technical, Economic and Environmental sustainability of the production line will be demonstrated, in particular competitive solar electricity generation costs, taking advantage of the high efficiency and/or intrinsic bi-faciality of the selected technologies. In particular, the latter feature will ensure higher annual energy production and hence significantly lower LCOE (10 to 15%) than conventional technologies. These expected outcomes will be assessed and evaluated as a solid milestone for the viability of the first GWp factory in Europe.

The three core technical work packages WP3, WP4, and WP5, represents the skeleton of the project. In WP3, the new heterojunction solar cell technologies will be selected and improved for an implementation to the full-scale industrial production. The goal of WP4 is equivalent to WP3 but it is focused on the modules. Finally, WP3 and WP4 outputs are implemented and tested for WP5 on the full-scale production lines with an effort on the automation.

Within WP6, the reliability and the energy yield of the products is studied. WP7 and WP8 are the WPs dedicated to dissemination and exploitation of the results. The technical work-packages tasks are strongly inter-linked to achieve the final industrial target.

WP3 teamwork has focused on the identification of the major issues limiting efficiency in production-like environment. Industrial compatible solar cells have been produced on the pilot line of CEA-INES. Roadmap study to 22.5% average efficiency in continuous production has been fixed and completed with solutions and has been transferred to Catania manufacturing line, and outlooks towards 23.5%. A metrology equipment to characterize HJT cell passivation layers has been developed in WP5 and will be tested in WP3.

WP4 main outcomes are the transfer of the best method for module production to EGP site, together with the industrial demonstration of new generation SmartWire technology in Meyer Burger. Target is to achieve 380Wp with 72cell modules. Simulations have been performed to evaluate the module performance for different cell interconnections, highlighting the best configuration to reach module optimal power. Mechanical analysis (simulation and bending tests) had been performed. In the same WP4 a cell to module (CTM) performance criterion has been studied for the different technologies of interest. Moreover, a consistent methodology to measure bifacial devices has already been proposed in the frame of the elaboration of the IEC 60904-1-2.

WP6 activity is focused on the reliability and performances study of products related to WP3 and WP4. Current standards demonstrate only the capability of modules to avoid early infant mortality but is not able to guarantee both reliability and durability. There is the need to define new accelerated ageing protocols beyond current standards. In this scenario Cell and module round-robin has been closed revealing the validity of the measurement procedure developed in the AMPERE environment. Outdoor performance measurements are on going in Cadarache (France) and Catania (Italy) sites. Moreover, a panel of innovative encapsulant have been characterized in extensive degradation tests.

III. AMPERE MANUFACTURING LINE PRELIMINARY OUTCOMES

Respect to the original AMPERE project timeframe, EGP has decided to anticipate to 2019 the installation and start-up of a second manufacturing line, leading the EGP 3SUN Catania site to a nominal capacity of 200 MWp. This will allow strengthening the demonstration of the viability of HJT solar module massive production in Europe.

A main project's Key Exploitable Result is to develop innovative automation solutions for wafers, cells and modules transportation and handling along the whole production line, re-using as much as possible of the existing infrastructure [2].

A complete HJT automated cell and module manufacturing line has been installed at EGP Catania site. The manufacturing

line process qualification tests are running and the mass production start up is forecasted for the month of July 2019. The first test run results are now available. In April and May 2019, more than 90'000 HJT complete cells have been manufactured. The Efficiency distribution is displayed in Fig.2

Fig. 2. Cell Efficiency Distribution at EGP Manufacturing line during process setup phase (April-May2019).

The average Efficiency is 22.1% with a standard deviation of 0.28% and an Efficiency Yield of 95%. The best cell efficiency has been 23%. The AMPERE project performance targets for Cell Manufacturing line are below reported:

- Best Cell efficiency: 23%
- Average Cell efficiency 22.5%
- $3\sigma < 4\%$
- Production scrap rate $< 2\%$
- Throughput > 2400 wf/h
- Process capability for M2 wafer, thickness 130-160 μ m

The Efficiency roadmap to reach the 22.5% target is related to material quality improvements (i.e. low resistivity wafers, Ag-Paste, etc.), process improvements (CVD, PVD screen printer process optimization) and full automation implementation (queue time reduction, cell sorting, etc.).

The full automated manufacturing line design is showed in the following Fig.3

Fig. 3. Design of AMPERE Automated Cell and Module lines.

The complete automation systems, including MES (Manufacturing Execution System) and SPC (Statistical Process Control) and data Analytics Tools is in the development and qualification phase and will be implemented within the mass production start-up in July 2019.

As example of the possible tools for Reporting and Process Control a batch by batch Efficiency Trend graph is reported in Fig.4.

Fig. 4. SPC - Cell Efficiency Trend during Cell Line qualification

IV. CONCLUSION

A premium technology with high efficiency, high reliability, and low LCOE will be industrialized in Europe, through the AMPERE project.

We are starting-up an innovative full-scale automated 200MWp/y production line of HJT bifacial cells and modules at the Enel Green Power 3SUN fab in Catania (Italy). Moreover, the processes, methods, techniques, automation systems developed in the project represent an innovation with respect to the market situation and with respect to the current practice in Industry

AMPERE is providing investment pathways for the exploitation of the results to support the GW factory.

Acknowledge: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon2020 Program under Grant Agreement N° 745601.

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